

Intra-Phrasal Construction: A Two-Layer Framework for Word Order Constraints

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2026.01.17

1 Introduction

This paper focuses on the fact that word order inside a phrase remains strongly constrained even in immediate, online speech. We propose a framework that treats such constraints as intra-phrasal constructions. While spontaneous speech often involves omission, repairs, and flexible ordering across phrases, the internal ordering of a phrase tends to be rigid. This suggests that speakers do not fully assemble phrases from scratch but rather retrieve them as optimized chunks. We argue that intra-phrasal rigidity is best accounted for by a two-layer view: one layer motivated by universal bio-resource constraints (processing speed, working memory, recoverability, and repair cost), and another layer shaped by language-specific local implementations (lexicalization, historical conventions, and morphosyntactic patterns). Although these factors are both real, their boundary appears mixed and chaotic in actual usage, which we treat as a fundamental property of intra-phrasal constructions.

2 Observation

In immediate speech, ordering across phrases can be flexible: speakers omit arguments, insert parenthetical material, and repair utterances on the fly. However, the internal ordering of a phrase is notably rigid. For example, English allows *a green apple* but not *apple green* in the same meaning, and *in front of a door* cannot be reordered as *of front in a door*. This asymmetry suggests that phrase-internal grammar operates under stronger constraints than inter-phrase organization.

For example, in English, the adjective-noun order in *the only way* is fixed, and the reordered form *the way only* does not convey the same meaning. Similarly, in prepositional phrases, *because of the rain* is acceptable, while *of because the rain* is not. These examples illustrate that intra-phrasal word order is stabilized as a chunk for fast retrieval.

This intra-phrasal rigidity is not limited to English; it is also observed in Japanese. The following examples indicate that intra-phrasal word order is stabilized as a chunk rather than assembled step by step.

Verb / auxiliary order:

rare tabemasu (cf. *taberaremasu*)
("eat-PASS/POT-POL")

Noun phrase order:

ie no watashi (cf. *watashi no ie*)
("house of me" vs. "my house")

Adjective–noun order:

kami shiroi (cf. *shiroi kami*)
("paper white" vs. "white paper")

Analogy-based misformation:

mitte (from *miru*) by false analogy with *kitte* (from *kiru*)

Similarly, Japanese verb forms show strong intra-phrasal rigidity. For example, the form **eiga wo mitte imasu* does not naturally occur. This misformation can be explained as an analogy-based error: the verb *miru* ("see") is misanalyzed as a five-grade (godan) verb, yielding an incorrect *mitte*-type form. This suggests that phrase-internal verb forms are operated as stabilized patterns (including conjugation

Figure 1: Two-layer view of intra-phrasal constructions: universal constraints and local implementations. Intra-phrasal word order tends to be stabilized as a chunk for fast retrieval, whereas inter-phrasal ordering allows flexibility through omission, repair, and insertion.

classes) rather than assembled freely step by step. Taken together, these patterns suggest that phrase-internal forms are retrieved as stabilized chunks under strong constraints, even in immediate speech.

3 Theoretical insight

In traditional generative grammar, word order is often described as the outcome of step-by-step assembly. However, this view struggles to explain the robustness of intra-phrasal word order. It is more natural to think that speakers retrieve phrases as chunks, whose internal order is stabilized. This stabilization should not be reduced to a single theoretical source.

4 Relation to previous studies

Research on intra-phrasal word order constraints is diverse. First, explanations based on universal constraints include word order optimization for reduced processing load (Yngve 1960; Hawkins 1994), word order selection based on information structure (Lambrecht 1994; Prince 1997), word order constraints based on recoverability of reference (Gibson 1998; Wasow 2002), and word order selection based on repair cost (Ferreira and Dell 2000; Jaeger 2010). On the other hand, explanations based on local implementations include language-specific lexicalization patterns (Bybee 2006; Croft 2001), word order changes based on historical developments (Newmeyer 2005; Hopper and Traugott 2003), word order fixation based on conventions (Goldberg 2006; Fillmore, Kay, and O'Connor 1988), and word order constraints based on morphosyntactic patterns (Baker 2003; Carnie 2013). While each of these studies provides important insights, they have not yet been fully integrated from the perspective of the two-layer view of intra-phrasal constructions.

5 Proposal: Intra-phrasal construction

We propose the term *intra-phrasal construction* to refer to phrase-internal patterns that are retrieved as optimized units rather than assembled step by step. Such units can be described as chunks: compact, high-speed retrievable packages whose internal order is stabilized. Importantly, this stabilization should not be reduced to a single theoretical source.

6 Two-layer view

We argue that intra-phrasal rigidity is shaped by two layers. The first layer is universal and arises from bio-resource constraints such as processing speed, working memory limitations, recoverability of reference, and repair cost. The second layer is a local implementation layer, shaped by language-specific lexicalization, historical developments, conventions, and morphosyntactic patterns. These two factors are both real, yet their boundary is not clean in actual usage. Instead, they appear mixed and chaotic, which is itself a defining property of intra-phrasal constructions.(Figure 1)

7 Conclusion

The two-layer framework of intra-phrasal constructions offers a new perspective on understanding word order constraints. By considering the interaction between universal constraints and local implementations, we can account for both cross-linguistic patterns and language-specific peculiarities. Future research will aim to validate this framework using concrete linguistic data and pursue further theoretical development.

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